

When less data is better: Privacy-by-design and bias reduction in AI-based human resource analytics and corporate social responsibility

Cristina IANCU, Simona-Vasilica OPREA*, Adela BĂRA, Denisa-Maria IORDACHE

Department of Economic Informatics and Cybernetics, Bucharest University of Economic Studies, Bucharest, Romania

*Corresponding author. E-mail: simona.oprea@csie.ase.ro

Abstract The use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Human Resource (HR)-related processes raises ethical and legal concerns, within the European context governed by the GDPR. This study proposes an approach to securing HR data by using Large Language Models-LLMs (Llama3.2, Mistral-Nemo, Gemma3), deployed on self-hosted infrastructure, which acts as a security middleware. The methodology includes two experiments applied to a multinational corporation dataset: (1) Automated Personally Identifiable Information (PII) redaction based on semantic context; (2) Measuring the impact of anonymization on *promotion* decisions. The results demonstrate that removing protected attributes using LLMs preserves the accuracy of performance predictions while reducing the “noise” that contributes to gender and ethnic bias. While 88% of LLM evaluations remain neutral under PII visibility, a persistent minority (12%) faces score alterations, which predictive models successfully forecasted with 93.2% accuracy. Furthermore, Bayesian causal discovery confirmed geographic region as the primary bias driver, with non-European candidates suffering mean score penalties up to -0.190, while European females gained up to +0.039 for Gemma3 model. Thus, a decentralized architecture, processing data on-premise, represents the optimal solution to balance technological innovation with fundamental employee rights. The results provides technical validation of the *data minimization* principle, demonstrating that protecting employee identity is an essential step for legal compliance and for building trustworthy AI systems.

Keywords: ethics and privacy; HR data governance; machine learning; large language models; corporation practice

1. Introduction

The intersection of AI and HR management (HRM) has come up to an increasing academic attention, particularly as organizations tend to integrate AI technologies into decision-making processes across the employee lifecycle. As organizations integrate more automated algorithmic systems for employee evaluation, performance prediction and workforce analytics, the tension between analytical utility and privacy preservation has emerged as an important area of academic interest, pointing out significant concerns regarding the ethical handling of PII. The regulatory landscape governing data processing in the European Union, particularly the GDPR enacted in 2018 and the more recent EU AI Act, mandates strict adherence to principles of data minimization and purpose limitation. Article 5(1)(c) of the GDPR explicitly requires that personal data be “adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary in relation to the purposes for which they are processed”. This regulatory imperative raises a research question for data scientists and organizational researchers: *Does the removal of personal identifiers, undertaken in service of regulatory compliance and ethical data stewardship, compromise the analytical value derived from machine learning models?*

The present investigation seeks to provide a grounded response to this question through methodical comparative analysis. The primary purpose of our study is to demonstrate that the anonymization of HR datasets, specifically through the removal of direct personal identifiers, does not result in appreciable degradation of machine learning (ML) model performance. This demonstration serves multiple interconnected objectives that span both theoretical and practical domains. From a theoretical perspective, our research contributes to on the topic of privacy-preserving ML by providing evidence that personal identifiers function as noise rather than signal in predictive modeling contexts. The intuition underlying this hypothesis is straightforward: an employee’s name or identification number bears no causal relationship to their performance outcomes, attrition risk or other variables of organizational interest. From a practical perspective, this research provides actionable guidance at the intersection of data science and data protection. Organizations frequently hesitate to implement anonymization procedures due to concerns about analytical degradation; this case study directly addresses such concerns by demonstrating that ethical data handling need not entail sacrifice of analytical utility.

Therefore, our study presents an empirical investigation into the fundamental question of whether personal identifiers, such as employee names, gender and location contribute meaningfully to the predictive capacity of ML models trained on human resources datasets. We directly address the data governance requirements of the EU AI Act (Article 10), which mandates that training, validation and testing datasets for high-risk AI systems must be subject to appropriate data governance and management practices.

2. Literature review

The vast number of papers published over the past five years reflects an intensifying interest in the operational and strategic applications of AI in HR (Iancu and Oprea 2025). The employee lifecycle possesses many stages in which AI has been already deployed with an impressive, fasted pace, thriving from recruitment and performance appraisal to learning and development. In recruitment, studies point to AI's value in aiding with the evaluation of a candidate in sourcing, screening and assessments. Automated systems can parse thousands of resumes, flag ideal candidates and even assess behavioral cues through video analysis, reducing hiring time and human error (Malin et al. 2024). (Madanchian 2024) highlight how tools like chatbots, Applicant Tracking Systems (ATS) and algorithmic filters improve recruiter productivity and reduce administrative burdens. Similarly, (Malin et al. 2024) present an experimental study showing how algorithmic recommendations influenced decision-making in candidate selection, but they also caution about "automation bias" that may override human judgment.

Performance management and learning also benefit from AI's analytical power. Dăniloia describes how AI tracks performance metrics in real time and recommends targeted learning based on gaps (Dăniloia 2024). These systems facilitate adaptive learning, ensuring that employee development is personalized and continuous. In the broader context of workforce analytics, the evolution of HR technologies highlights an important transition from descriptive data processing to advanced predictive modeling. Emphasizing the strategic value of unstructured employee feedback, (Tanasescu et al. 2022) demonstrate the necessity of robust Big Data Extraction, Transformation and Loading processes to perform scalable text mining on employee reviews, illustrating how sentiment analysis can distill vast amounts of qualitative data into actionable insights. Building upon this interest in the objectivity of data, a subsequent study by (Tanasescu et al. 2024) explores the application of sophisticated ML algorithms to forecast employee performance, ensuring that ML models evaluate merit rather than perpetuating historical human biases.

Additionally, (Ekuma 2024) conducted a systematic review exploring how AI and automation are transforming the field of HR development (HRD), particularly through the automation of training, performance evaluation and knowledge dissemination functions. The review raises concerns about ethical dilemmas, including job displacement, deskilling and digital surveillance. The authors point out that current HRD literature largely overlooks the governance and regulatory aspects of AI deployment, particularly in relation to ethical compliance and data protection

Another study outlines the four "I" model (intentionality, integration, implementation, indication), proposed as a guiding framework to ethically and strategically deploy AI in HR processes (Grigoryan et al. 2025). The authors also highlight a "productivity paradox," suggesting that while AI is expected to improve efficiency, its effects may not always translate into measurable productivity gains due to poor implementation, staff resistance or lack of alignment with organizational goals. The need for structured frameworks to guide AI integration in HR is further emphasized by (Tolici and Niculescu 2025) offering a comprehensive conceptual model rooted in theories such as Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), the Resource-Based View (RBV) and Socio-Technical Systems Theory. Also, (Sony et al. 2025) deepen this concern with a systematic analysis of algorithmic bias in recruitment systems. They confirm that biased training data perpetuate discriminatory patterns (especially gender and racial bias) unless explicitly corrected. In support of this, (Bujold et al. 2023) conduct a review of empirical studies and suggest that AI adoption must prioritize stakeholder participation and be evaluated through ethical impact assessments, not just business KPIs. The authors highlight the breadth of AI applications across six HRM functions, such as talent acquisition, performance evaluation, talent management, workforce planning, health and wellbeing, compensation and the types of AI algorithms employed, such as descriptive, predictive and prescriptive systems.

Gélinas et al. draw attention to how continuous monitoring, algorithmic decision-making and opaque models diminish employee autonomy (Gélinas, Sadreddin, and Vahidov 2022). In response, several scholars argue for *privacy-by-design* as a default principle in AI-HRM tools (Batool, Zowghi, and Bano 2023), proposing governance strategies that include algorithmic audits, employee representation in AI governance boards and differential privacy mechanisms to reduce identification risks. (Hernández 2024) introduces a multidimensional framework grounded in transparency, inclusivity and stakeholder participation, asserting that AI governance must go beyond compliance to foster organizational justice. (Aizenberg and van den Hoven 2020) shift the conversation from empirical evaluation to a normative framework grounded in human rights. They critique current AI regulatory models as overly functionalist and technically fragmented, arguing that they insufficiently account for the political and legal contexts in which AI operates. For HRM applications, this implies a shift in design logic from “what can be done” to “what should be done”, particularly when managing sensitive employee data or automated recruitment processes. The authors also recommend the integration of Explainable AI (XAI) principles into future tools.

Another relevant study (Wagh 2025) focuses on AI and automation within HR training, exploring how intelligent systems are redefining how organizations manage skills development and employee learning. (Ussher-Eke 2025) provides an exhaustive analysis of how HR can operationalize GDPR principles through data minimization, consent management and cross-border transfer governance, underscoring the pivotal role of HR as both a data custodian and compliance actor, especially given the sensitivity of employee records (e.g., health, behavior, salary). Additionally, (Sadeghi 2024) investigates employee perceptions of AI use in the workplace, identifying high levels of distrust and anxiety when AI tools are perceived as intrusive or unaccountable.

Despite the abundance of studies, several important gaps remain. There is a significant lack of empirical validation, noting a shortage of longitudinal studies that explore how AI use in HR evolves over time and affects workforce trust and inclusion generated by lack of objectivism. Furthermore, few papers directly address how AI tools comply with the European Union’s AI Act, nor do they explore tools for Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA). Therefore, our study contributes to addressing the empirical gap in the implementation and evaluation of responsible AI systems in HRM. By proposing and testing a privacy-by-design AI toolkit using synthetic HR data, this research aims to demonstrate how ethical principles, such as anonymization, can be embedded operationally into AI-enabled HR processes, so that subjective bias can be overcome.

3. Methodology

To address the research objective of this paper, we propose a multi-step methodology grounded in the principles of a decentralized AI deployment that focuses on personal data protection and privacy. The proposed workflow is composed of eight sequential steps, each of which contributes to ensuring GDPR compliance while preserving predictive utility. Table 1 reflects each step, its purpose, the methods used to achieve it, input and reason.

Table 1. Methodology steps

Step	Objective (What)	Mechanism (How)	Input	Rationale (Why)
1. Data definition & sampling	Establish the foundational dataset for the experiment.	Sub-sampling a synthetic HR dataset from Kaggle to a computationally viable size.	Raw HR Dataset containing PII and professional data.	To provide a baseline of candidate profiles that mimic real-world HR data.
2. DPIA report generation	Assess risks and justify lawful processing.	Providing the LLM a prompt that asks it to generate the report.	Sampled HR dataset from Step 1.	To generate a risk assessment report based on high-risk attributes identified.
3. Profile construction	Create a privacy-preserving version of the candidate profiles.	Simply removing the <i>sensitive</i> information from the candidate’s profile.	Sampled HR dataset from Step 1.	To ensure dual-condition candidate representations.

4. Controlled prompt variation	Design the testing mechanism to trigger potential biases.	Formulating prompts that ask the AI to rate promotion suitability of each candidate (provides a rating from 1 to 10).	1. Nominal (full) profile. 2. Anonymized profile: a. without name; b. without name and location.	To test the model's sensitivity to PII fields changes in candidate's profile.
5. Bias AI evaluation	Generate the delta score.	Feeding both the nominal and anonymized profiles to the LLMs at temperature = 0.	Nominal prompts and anonymized prompts.	To establish the mathematical bias.
6. Feature engineering	Prepare the output data for advanced statistical testing.	Consolidating the LLMs outputs into a <i>master dataset</i> for each candidate. Using NLP for gender inference and grouping locations in regions.	Raw output scores from all 3 LLMs (Llama3.2, Gemma3, Mistral-Nemo) across both prompt variations.	To convert raw text names and synthetic cities into categorical vectors (male/female, continent) required for measuring demographic parity.
7. ML classification	Test the predictability and systemic nature of the detected bias.	Training ML classifiers: logistic regression, random forest, XGBoost to predict if bias_detected = True based on demographic and professional features.	Enriched master dataset.	To prove whether algorithmic discrimination is noise or a predictable flaw within the AI.
8. Bayesian causal discovery	Map the internal architecture of the LLMs' decision-making flow.	Executing dynamic topological rendering to draw DAGs using dynamic p-values, ANOVA and Pearson correlations.	The final classification metrics.	To prove <i>causation</i> over correlation, visualizing exactly how demographic data infects the evaluation score.

For a deeper understanding of these steps, the flowchart in Figure 1 provides a visual synthesis of the end-to-end analytical pipeline. The process starts by choosing randomly one candidate from the initial dataset and use it to fed a LLM (Llama3.2) prepared for identifying all the possible sensitive columns. Specifically, the model will be prompted to classify attributes into three categories depending on the risk level: direct PII, sensitive HR data and non-PII attributes. As output, the model generates a Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) report, used as guidance in the following steps.

Next, we draw five independent, non-overlapping random samples of 2.000 records from the original dataset of 2 million entries, which is be merged in one file of 10.000 records. The sampling is meant to ensure that the findings are not dependent on a particular subset of the data.

To evaluate the potential influence of PII, three profile variants are constructed for each candidate: a nominal version containing full demographic information, an anonymized version where name is removed and a latter version where both name and location are removed. These profiles are subsequently evaluated by three LLMs: Llama 3.2, Gemma 3 and Mistral-Nemo, which assign promotion suitability scores on a scale from 1 to 10. The scores will be added in a new column for each evaluated candidate, and the difference between the score obtained from the full profile and the anonymized profiles is interpreted as a quantitative indicator of potential algorithmic *bias*. Two more additional features will enhance the data by using NLP algorithms to determine the gender of each candidate and the corresponding geographical continent.

Figure 1. End-to-end methodological framework for AI bias detection in HR evaluative processes

Diving into the predictive phase, we apply three ML classifiers: logistic regression (LR), random forest (RF) and extreme gradient boosting (XGB), to determine whether algorithmic discrimination arises from random noise or represents a predictable flaw within the AI evaluation process. Finally, to investigate potential causal relationships, we employ Bayesian networks to visualize and quantify how demographic attributes may influence the evaluation scores.

3.1 Step 1-Data sourcing

The input dataset, HR Data – Multi National Company, is publicly available through the Kaggle open data platform¹. It represents a synthetically generated yet structurally realistic snapshot of HR data from a multinational organization, designed to reflect typical HR information systems used in both public and private sector institutions, summing up 2 million entries. While the data does not correspond to real individuals, its structure, distributions and variable interdependencies mirror real HR data environments, making it suitable for this methodological research which targets privacy, compliance and responsible AI.

The dataset consists of a tabular structure containing twelve core variables that collectively describe employee attributes, employment conditions and performance-related indicators. These variables include: unique employee identifiers, full names, job titles, departmental assignments, years of professional experience, employment status, salary information, work modality (e.g., remote or on-site), geographic location, performance ratings and hire dates. From a data protection perspective, the dataset is valuable because it contains a combination of direct identifiers (such as employee names and IDs), quasi-identifiers (such as job title, department, location and hire date) and sensitive or high-risk attributes (including salary levels and performance evaluations), allowing for the construction of advanced analytical tasks such as attrition modeling, performance prediction and promotion suitability analysis, while simultaneously raising concerns regarding profiling, fairness and employee surveillance. As such, the dataset supports predictive modeling and also the examination of ethical and legal implications associated with automated decision-making in employment contexts.

Thus, the dataset plays a dual methodological role. First, it serves as the input layer for developing and validating a privacy-by-design toolkit that integrates anonymization and automated DPIA generation. The presence of identifiable and sensitive attributes enables an evaluation of how privacy-preserving techniques affect data utility, analytical accuracy and regulatory compliance. Second, the dataset is used to demonstrate that meaningful HR analytics is performed on anonymized data without relying on direct personal identifiers, supporting the GDPR principles of data minimization and purpose limitation.

Let D denote the stratified and sampled HR dataset, containing both personal identifiers and job-related attributes. Formally:

$$D = \{X_p, X_n, Y\} \quad (1)$$

where X_p represents PII, such as names, locations or gender; X_n represents non-sensitive, job-relevant features (skills, experience, performance indicators); Y denotes the target variable used for prediction (recruitment outcome or performance score). The structure of the dataset is presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Snippet of data used in analysis

Employee_ID	EMP0000001	EMP0000002	EMP0000003	EMP0000004	EMP0000005
Full_Name	Joshua Nguyen	Julie Williams	Alyssa Martinez	Nicholas Valdez	Joel Hendricks
Department	IT	Marketing	HR	IT	Operations
Job_Title	Software Engineer	SEO Specialist	HR Manager	Software Engineer	Logistics Coordinator
Hire_Date	10.08.2011	02.03.2018	20.03.2023	12.10.2023	09.12.2024
Location	Isaacland, Denmark	Anthonside, Costa Rica	Port Christinaport, Saudi Arabia	Port Shelbychester, Antigua and Barbuda	Lake Kimberly, Palestinian Territory
Performance_Rating	5	2	1	1	5
Experience_Years	14	7	2	1	0
Status	Resigned	Active	Active	Active	Active
Work_Mode	On-site	On-site	On-site	On-site	On-site
Salary_INR	1585363	847686	1430084	990689	535082

¹ <https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/rohitgrewal/hr-data-mnc>

3.2 Step 2-DPIA report generation

This research implements an automated mechanism for generating DPIAs by involving a locally deployed LLM (Llama3.2), instantiated through the Ollama LLM framework. The purpose of this step comes from the need to emphasize the implications of analyzing personal data. The decision to deploy the model locally rather than via a cloud-based API is significant, as it prevents unauthorized third-party access and aligns with data privacy requirements.

The process is operationalized through a prompt template that explicitly instructs the LLM to assume the role of a *data protection analyst* and to produce a structured, semantically rich DPIA report for each individual employee record. The prompt engineering strategy ensures consistency across outputs while preserving contextual sensitivity to the specific attributes of each record. The model is provided with a controlled set of input variables corresponding to the selected HR data fields, including job title, department, years of experience, salary level, performance rating, work modality, employment status and hire date.

For the processed record, the LLM performs a multi-dimensional assessment that mirrors the analytical structure required by regulatory guidance. Specifically, the model identifies the categories of personal and potentially sensitive data involved, evaluates foreseeable privacy and ethical risks such as re-identification, unfair profiling, salary disclosure or algorithmic bias and articulates an appropriate legal basis for processing in accordance with GDPR provisions, including contractual necessity, legitimate interest or explicit consent. In addition, the model generates mitigation strategies, recommending concrete technical and organizational safeguards such as role-based access controls, encryption of data at rest and in transit, anonymization or pseudonymization mechanisms and audit logging. This step only acts as an intermediary, separate piece of the pipeline. Its output contributes to a better understanding of an employee personal information, shaping the guidelines of an objective, accurate analysis of his profile. Table 3 provides an example of a report generated for a single record.

Table 3. Sample of a record-based DPIA report

<p><i>DPIA report</i></p> <p><i>Here is the classification of HR data fields into the four categories:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Employee_ID: High Risk (Direct PII)</i> • <i>Full_Name: High Risk (Direct PII)</i> • <i>Department: Low Risk (Non-PII)</i> • <i>Job_Title: Medium Risk (Sensitive HR Data)</i> • <i>Hire_Date: Medium Risk (Sensitive HR Data)</i> • <i>Location: Medium Risk (Sensitive HR Data)</i> • <i>Performance_Rating: Medium Risk (Sensitive HR Data)</i> • <i>Experience_Years: Medium Risk (Sensitive HR Data)</i> • <i>Status: Low Risk (Non-PII)</i> • <i>Work_Mode: Low Risk (Non-PII)</i> • <i>Salary_INR: High Risk (Direct PII)</i> <p><i>Mitigation strategy:</i></p> <p><i>To mitigate the risks, we will implement data minimization by only processing essential employee information for promotion purposes and preventing bias by ensuring that performance ratings are not solely based on salary or job title.</i></p>

The DPIA output informs the selection of manipulated identity variables (name and location), which were classified as high-risk attributes and therefore selected for counterfactual testing.

3.3 Step 3-Profile construction

To further explore the implications of using PII in automated HR decision-making, this study conducted a controlled experiment designed to evaluate potential bias in LLM outputs. The research investigated whether the presence of identity-related details, specifically candidate names, would influence the evaluation of employee suitability for promotion by an LLM. The underlying hypothesis posits that if the AI model produces different ratings for the same candidate when PII is visible versus anonymized, it may

be implicitly relying on gender, ethnicity or culture-based cues in its decision-making process, thereby introducing systemic bias.

The experimental design employs a comparative framework in which three versions of the dataset were constructed and subjected to identical ML pipelines. The first version, designated as the *original dataset*, retained all fields including personal identifiers (full_name and location). The second version, designated as the *anonymized dataset*, was constructed by removing only the name and then *the second anonymized dataset* removed also the location, while retaining all other attributes in their original, unmodified form. Thus, a transformation function f_{LLM} is applied:

$$X'_p = f_{LLM}(X_p) \quad (2)$$

Making the resulting anonymized dataset as being:

$$D' = \{X'_p, X_n, Y\} \quad (3)$$

By isolating the effect of personal identifier removal, we establish an experimental comparison that directly addresses the question of whether these specific fields contribute predictive value. More aggressive anonymization techniques, while valuable for achieving stronger privacy guarantees, would confound our analysis by introducing multiple simultaneous changes to the data structure.

3.4 Step 4-Controlled prompt variation

Driven by the critical need to uncover latent intersectional and cognitive biases within hiring algorithms, we develop and execute an experiment utilizing a custom LLM-based bias audit framework. Three open-weights LLMs are selected: Llama3.2 (USA), Mistral-Nemo (EU) and Gemma3 (a localized variant of Gemini). An important component of this methodology is that these models are run strictly on-premise, locally.

The *controlled prompt variation* strategy sets up the fundamental baseline of the experiment: if the model's internal logic is objective, presenting it with mathematically identical professional profiles, differing only in the presence of a name or location, should yield perfectly identical promotional ratings. Thus, the role of the LLM is not predictive, but transformational: it processes the raw textual attributes in X_p and produces an anonymized representation X'_p .

3.5 Step 5-Bias evaluation design

Any statistically significant deviation from this baseline serves as quantifiable evidence of algorithmic bias triggered by demographic markers, computed by the difference between the two scores:

$$Bias_i = Score_{PII} - Score_{Anonymized} \quad (4)$$

The prompt is:

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""You are a senior hiring manager at a multinational corporation.
You need to rate this employee's profile for a promotion consideration.
CANDIDATE PROFILE:
- Full Name: {full_name}
- Current Job Title: {job_title}
- Department: {department}
- Years of Experience: {experience_years}
- Current Performance Rating: {performance_rating}/5.0
- Current Salary: {salary}
- Location: {location}
- Work Mode: {work_mode}
- Employment Status: {status}
Based on this profile, rate this candidate's suitability for promotion on a
scale of 1-10.
Provide ONLY a single number between 1 and 10, nothing else.
Rating: ""

```

For the first anonymous dataset, the prompt differs only by lacking full name, and for the second one, both full name and location.

3.6 Step 6-Feature engineering

Before advancing to the causal analysis, it is necessary to structure the outputs resulted from applying the previously described models. There are nine raw outputs evaluated under multiple anonymization

conditions, which served as the primary input, three for each of the LLMs used: one after analysing the full data, one after removing name, while the last one being the experiment run on the dataset that also had the location removed. We compute the score shifts between all the three outputs, which are described in Table 4.

Table 4. Description for the new columns

Delta NameOnly	rating full – rating no name	Score shift – nameless profile
Delta Total	rating full – rating anonymized	Full PII score minus fully anonymized score
Bias Detected	1 if $ \text{Delta Total} > 0$, else 0	Binary classification target of bias

Next, we enhance the dataframe with two new demographic vectors, engineered to enable intersectional bias testing. Firstly, we use a NLP deterministic algorithm for the candidates’ first names, to infer gender classifications that will help us provide the categorical variable necessary to measure demographic parity. Second, to evaluate potential geographic or xenophobic bias, we implement a macro-regional mapping methodology. The isolated country string from each candidate’s synthetic location is standardized into an ISO-3166 alpha-2 country code and we programmatically map them to one of the six distinct continental macro-regions (i.e. Europe, Australia/Oceania, South America, North America, Asia and Africa). Afterwards, we convert the dataset to long format, with one row per each employee and model combination, thus reaching out 30.000 training observations that enable the LLM architecture itself to be used as a predictive feature.

3.7 Step7-Predictive modeling

The next stage of the methodology aims to move beyond descriptive statistics, seeking to uncover the underlying causal mechanisms driving the observed algorithmic behaviors. In this phase, we took the enriched dataset and applied a suite of ML classifiers alongside Bayesian causal discovery techniques.

To achieve this, we frame the bias audit as a predictive classification task. Using the bias delta, the difference between a candidate’s nominal score and their anonymized score, we engineer a binary target variable indicating whether a candidate was unjustly penalized by the AI upon the revelation of their personal data (`bias_detected = True`). The target variable is chosen because the objective of this phase was not to predict candidate performance, but rather to predict the AI’s discriminatory behavior itself. Then, we train three ML algorithms: LR, RF and XGB to predict this penalty based entirely on the candidates’ demographic and professional features. This selection of models is on purpose, as LR served as a necessary baseline to test for simple, linear discrimination, while the tree-based ensemble models (RF and XGB) are deployed to capture complex, non-linear relationships. By analyzing feature importance within these predictive models, we isolate which inputs, such as a specific geographic region or gender marker, most heavily influence an LLM’s decision to alter a candidate’s score. The standard classification metrics such as accuracy or AUC are used to compare the predictive performance of models operating on the original datasets against those operating on the semantically anonymized datasets.

3.8 Step 8-Bayesian causal discovery

Finally, we apply causal discovery, but not for seeking to reverse-engineer the internal architecture of the LLMs. We intend to model structural dependencies between demographic attributes, professional features and the probability of bias manifestation. The objective is therefore to examine whether demographic attributes act as upstream determinants in the bias formation process under controlled experimental conditions. Thus, we apply Bayesian causal discovery techniques to construct a Directed Acyclic Graph (DAG) that transitions the analysis from correlational observation to causal inference. The Bayesian Network topology is enforced by a combination of structure learning algorithms and conditional probability extractions, validated through statistical dependency tests including Chi-Square contingency analysis, one-way ANOVA and Cramér’s V effect size computations.

4. Results

4.1 Performance score estimation

The comparative outputs produced by the three evaluated LLMs based on the five samples of candidate profiles are summarized in Table 5. The high consistency of bias rates across all five sampling rounds within each model confirms that we achieve stable, replicable properties of each architecture. We can see

architecture-specific sensitivity to individual name stimuli when looking at the results for the nameless profiles. For example, sample C exhibited the highest bias incidence and the most extreme negative score delta in Mistral-Nemo. However, it produced the lowest name-removal bias rate across Llama3.2 samples. Such a cross-model inversion is consistent with different LLMs encoding distinct demographic associations for the same names. This suggests that name anonymisation alone is insufficient and that location redaction is equally necessary.

Table 5. Per-sample LLMs output statistics

Model	Sample	No name		No name and location	
	2,000	bias (%)	Score delta Mean (Std. dev)	bias (%)	Score delta Mean (Std. dev)
Gemma3	A	13.3%	0.070 (0.399)	16.4%	-0.025 (0.492)
	B	11.8%	0.060 (0.380)	15.4%	-0.020 (0.501)
	C	13.3%	0.062 (0.402)	16.7%	-0.013 (0.494)
	D	13.1%	0.057 (0.421)	15.8%	-0.037 (0.500)
	E	11.7%	0.058 (0.392)	16.4%	-0.021 (0.463)
Mistral-Nemo	A	6.8%	0.066 (0.557)	9.3%	-0.154 (0.955)
	B	6.9%	0.070 (0.631)	9.7%	-0.216 (1.052)
	C	8.5%	0.068 (0.683)	11.6%	-0.280 (1.125)
	D	7.8%	0.106 (0.661)	11.3%	-0.217 (1.077)
	E	8.0%	0.096 (0.667)	10.3%	-0.184 (1.014)
Llama3.2	A	3.3%	-0.029 (0.362)	8.0%	0.014 (0.512)
	B	2.7%	-0.031 (0.329)	8.0%	0.012 (0.509)
	C	1.6%	-0.020 (0.246)	8.0%	0.043 (0.465)
	D	3.8%	-0.040 (0.426)	9.7%	0.019 (0.536)
	E	2.7%	-0.034 (0.341)	9.2%	0.024 (0.550)

Figure 2 illustrates the mean score delta per sampling round across both anonymization conditions, with error bars representing ± 1 standard error. In the name-removal condition (left panel), Gemma3 and Mistral-Nemo consistently produce positive deltas across all five samples, confirming that name visibility systematically inflates their assigned scores relative to the anonymous baseline. Llama3.2, by contrast, maintains negative deltas throughout, reinforcing its architecturally distinct tendency to suppress scores when names are disclosed. The right panel, which shows the values for full anonymization condition, reveals that it frequently penalizes profiles, when using the Mistral-Nemo model and especially Gemma3. By contrast, Llama3.2 moves above the zero line, scoring higher for anonymous profiles.

Figure 2. Mean score delta per sample and LLM

Moving forward to the aggregated outputs, one can notice that all three LLM architectures showed measurable bias that are contingent to candidate's, with substantial variation in magnitude across models.

As seen in Table 6, Gemma3 is by far the most biased model, with 25.3% of the profiles showing any bias, more than double the value of Llama3.2’s achievement. It also has the highest percent of bias in both modified profiles, meaning it’s the model most consistently responding to identity signals across multiple anonymisation steps.

Next, we continue with the directional analysis and discover architecturally distinct response profiles. Gemma3 and Mistral-Nemo both output a positive name effect, where identity visibility tended to inflate scores (76.88% and 70.88% of name-removal bias events resulted in higher scores, respectively), which reverses into a suppressive location effect under full anonymization. Location removal is a stronger trigger than name removal across all three models, suggesting that geographic context encodes identity signals at least as potently as the name itself. Llama3.2 is the most stable, with only 2.8% pure name-driven bias and just 1.3% both conditions, though its 8.6% location-triggered rate shows it is still not immune to geographic identity signals.

Table 6. Aggregate LLMs output statistics

Model	Bias incidence (N = 10,000)				Score direction		Mean score delta (Full PII – Anonymised)	
	Name removal	+ Location removal	Both conditions	Any bias	Higher (name)	Lower (name)	Name removal M (SD)	+ Location M (SD)
	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n	n		
Gemma3	1263 (12.6%)	1615 (16.2%)	768 (7.7%)	2526 (25.3%)	971	292	0.061 (0.399)	-0.023 (0.490)
Mistral-Nemo	759 (7.6%)	1041 (10.4%)	365 (3.6%)	1643 (16.4%)	538	221	0.081 (0.641)	-0.210 (1.047)
Llama3.2	282 (2.8%)	855 (8.6%)	127 (1.3%)	1080 (10.8%)	74	208	-0.031 (0.345)	0.022 (0.515)

4.2 Predictive classification of algorithmic bias

One of the important step in this predictive analysis is represented by the usage of ML classifiers, trained on the enhanced dataframe which we previously created. Because the target variable bias_detected is highly imbalanced (88.3% profiles did not show bias, while 11.7% did), we applied three complementary strategies: (1) class_weight='balanced' on Logistic Regression and Random Forest; (2) XGBoost’s inherent focus on misclassified examples through sequential residual fitting; and (3) stratify=y in the train/test split to preserve the 88/12 class ratio identically in training and test partitions, which were split by the 80%-20% rule. This whole process of preparing and applying the classifiers is shown in Figure 3.

The full pipeline is executed on each of the five samples in order to test generalization, and performance is evaluated using Accuracy, F1-score and ROC-AUC. For every metric, we compute its mean, standard deviation, also showing the limits of the interval in which the values range. The low variance across samples confirms that the findings are generalizable, rather than artifacts of a specific data partition and they reveal a nuanced contrast between linear and non-linear predictive capabilities, as in Table 7. The convergence of these metrics confirms that the LLMs’ discriminatory outputs are neither random anomalies nor isolated hallucinations.

Table 7. ML classifiers output

Model	Metric	Mean	Std Dev	Min	Max
Logistic Regression	Accuracy	0.647	0.008	0.631	0.659
	F1	0.488	0.007	0.478	0.495
	AUC	0.690	0.010	0.673	0.709
Random Forest	Accuracy	0.918	0.004	0.913	0.924
	F1	0.881	0.011	0.866	0.800
	AUC	0.948	0.004	0.943	0.954
XGBoost	Accuracy	0.930	0.003	0.926	0.935
	F1	0.840	0.013	0.817	0.863
	AUC	0.939	0.004	0.934	0.945

Figure 3. ML classifiers pipeline

A few factors determine that generalization is achieved: negligible AUC variance, consistent F1 scores and the performance gap between Logistic Regression and ensemble methods. Thus, LLM bias patterns are non-linearly separable and require ensemble methods. The low standard deviations across ten random states constitute a formal demonstration that the pipeline's performance claims are generalisable. Thus, in Table 8, the results after running the classifiers on the merged samples, summing up 10.000 records, are provided. Table 8. ML classifiers output for the aggregated dataset

Model	Accuracy	F1	AUC
Logistic Regression	0.647	0.479	0.673
Random Forest	0.921	0.888	0.943
XGBoost	0.932	0.845	0.934

Figure 4 visualizes the predictive power of all three classifiers. Almost perfect AUC scores of the ensemble methods carry a central implication that LLM scoring bias is not random, but it is structurally predictable from the combination of employee identity, regional context and model architecture. An AUC of 0.943 means the Random Forest correctly ranks a randomly chosen biased employee above a randomly chosen unbiased one 94.3% of the time.

Figure 4. ROC curves for ML models

Moving forward, Figure 5 isolates the specific variables that most heavily influence the LLM’s decision to alter a candidate’s score. By mapping the Gini impurity reduction across the Random Forest decision trees, it exposes the “triggers” of AI bias. The score difference between the full dataset and the nameless one matters 13.8% in the whole output, being the single most predictive feature, confirming that name-level identity signals are the dominant driver of LLM scoring bias. The low importance of Gender suggests that name-based gender inference does not substantially alter the LLMs’ evaluative behavior at the aggregate level, though this does not preclude the existence of localized gender effects within specific regional or professional subgroups. LLM bias is best predicted not by who the employee nominally is, but by how the model’s scoring actually shifts in response to identity revelation. Region’s moderate importance confirms the geographic penalty patterns observed, as it weighs more than the candidate’s department, meaning that it matters to a great extent to the LLM when deciding if worthy of a promotion. A finding with direct implications for AI fairness mitigation is that removing names from AI-evaluated profiles would eliminate the strongest single predictor of biased scoring.

The average score delta disaggregated by the intersection of geographic region and inferred gender can be observed in Figure 6. Negative values indicate that the presence of PII resulted in a lower evaluation score, while positive values indicate that PII conferred a scoring advantage. The most severely penalized intersectional group is Africa, where the gender could not be determined at $\Delta = -0.20$, but the males from Europe record the smallest negative delta at -0.02 , reflecting the fact that European men may be less affected than those from other regions. The Unknown region category, encoding missing geographic information, ranks among the most penalised, implying models treat geographic ambiguity as a negative signal rather than a neutral one. Only two intersectional groups receive a net positive delta: Europe women at $+0.03$ and Europe (Unknown) at $+0.03$. The European advantage, though small, suggests that Western-

sounding names and European locations may activate latent prestige associations within the models' training data.

Architectural Triggers of Discrimination (Feature Importance)

Figure 5. Triggers of discrimination-feature importance

The 'Delta Gravity' Map: Intersectional Score Penalties (Full PII - Fully Anonymized | Negative = PII Hurt Score)

Figure 6. Intersectional score penalties

In Figure 7, we present a violin plot, where each shape consists of score deltas distribution across gender categories. The tails represent rare cases of profiles whose score shifted a lot when identity is revealed.

Even if the scores are centered around value 0, the structure of the whisker denotes important differences. Mistral-Nemo shows the widest vertical extension for all gender categories and it has the biggest volatility among all models. It also has the longest downward tails across all gender groups, meaning that it penalizes some candidates harsher. Gemma3 has an elongated, flat body with separate blobs which are most pronounced for male profiles. They tell us that the shift is not gradual, as the model is making a binary decision for a subset of profiles: either the score stays the same (the big mass at 0) or it bumps up by exactly 1 point (the bubble). Also, Llama3.2 displays flat and shorter violins, making it the most stable and least reactive model to identity information. It is not strongly penalising, nor favouring anyone based on its demographic data.

Importantly, the violin shapes are largely symmetric across Male and Female categories within each model, further corroborating that gender-based differential treatment is not a primary driver of algorithmic bias in these LLMs. The Unknown gender category produces somewhat more asymmetric violin shapes, particularly for Mistral-Nemo, where the negative tail is more pronounced, suggesting that the model is responding more to other features found in the profile.

Figure 7. Violin plot-bias distribution by gender

Diving further into the region analysis, the grouped bar chart from Figure 8 presents the bias detection rate by continental macro-region for each LLM. Regions are ordered along the horizontal axis, and the overall average bias rate is indicated by a dashed line at approximately 11.6%. Gemma3 dominates as the most bias-prone model across virtually all regions. Its highest bias rate is observed when the region is unknown, a bit over 25%, the lowest being for both Asia and Europe at approximately 13.0%. In contrast, Llama3.2 and Mistral-Nemo showcase significantly lower and more uniform bias rates across regions, typically ranging between 7.5% and 11.5%, demonstrating that the susceptibility to geographic identity markers is not a universal property of language models but is architecture-specific. Gemma3’s elevated sensitivity to regional cues, particularly for candidates from Australia/Oceania and North America, may reflect specific biases encoded in its training corpus, as the model originates from the United States, which belongs to North America.

The LLMs evaluated in this study, Mistral-Nemo, Gemma3 and Llama3.2, demonstrate measurable sensitivity to personally identifiable information in candidate profiles. While the majority of evaluations remain stable under anonymization, a persistent minority (approximately 8-16% depending on model and demographic subgroup) output score changes that may be caused by the presence of name and location. The score difference is predominantly negative in direction (PII depresses scores), geographically stratified

(non-European regions are penalized more heavily) and performance focused (performance is the strongest predictor of bias activation). Still, the effects of gender are modest at the aggregate level, even though we can see localized disparities, based on region.

Figure 8. Bias rate by region

4.3. Bayesian causal discovery

Moving beyond the predictive classification of algorithmic bias, the following Bayesian causal discovery analysis isolates the precise structural mechanisms through which demographic identifiers infect the LLMs’ evaluative logic.

The objective is to determine whether demographic attributes, like geographic region and gender, operate as significant determinants in the bias formation process. We also aim to quantify the relative structural contribution of each variable taken into account, by implying a combination of statistical dependency testing and conditional probability extraction. A DAG is constructed to represent the hypothesised causal topology, with node placement enforced by theoretical priors concerning the temporal and structural ordering of variables: exogenous identity features at Tier 0, professional context features at Tier 1 and the bias outcome at Tier 2.

Structure learning is grounded in three complementary statistical procedures. Chi-square contingency analysis is applied to all categorical variable pairs to test for statistical independence, with edge inclusion requiring $p < 0.01$. Cramér’s V is computed as a normalised effect size measure, ranging from 0 (no association) to 1 (perfect association), enabling comparison of dependency strength across edges irrespective of sample size, as in Table 9. One-way ANOVA is applied to continuous predictors (Performance rating, Experience) against the binary bias outcome and to geographic and gender variables against the continuous score delta, to assess mean differences across categorical groups. DAG edges are drawn where statistical significance and a minimum effect size threshold of $V \geq 0.025$ or $F \geq 10.0$ were both satisfied; edges failing to meet either criterion are retained as weak or indirect paths if theoretically motivated. All tests are conducted on the full 30,000 observation long-format dataset, comprising 10,000 employee profiles evaluated by three LLM architectures.

Table 9. Statistical dependency tests

Variable pair	Cramér's V	χ^2	p-value	Sig.
Model→Bias	0.129	495.0	< 0.001	***
Status→Bias	0.140	584.6	< 0.001	***
Region→Bias	0.043	54.3	< 0.001	***
Performance→Bias	0.035	36.1	< 0.001	***
Department→Bias	0.025	18.4	0.005	**

Gender→Bias	0.006	0.94	0.626	ns
Gender→Region	0.024	33.7	< 0.001	***
Region→Department	0.025	112.6	< 0.001	***
One-way ANOVA, continuous predictors				
Performance→Bias (ANOVA)	F = 62.12	—	< 0.001	***
Experience→Bias (ANOVA)	F = 15.87	—	< 0.001	***
Region→ΔScore (ANOVA)	F = 27.13	—	< 0.001	***
Gender→ΔScore (ANOVA)	F = 17.34	—	< 0.001	***

To further investigate the subjectivity of LLMs using causality, in Table 10, we provide the mean score delta for all 14 regions and gender groups. All the observations are tested against a null hypothesis of zero effect using one-sample t -tests. It is visible that under the full anonymisation condition thirteen of the fourteen identity groups output negative mean deltas, which brings us to the conclusion that when identity is visible, scores get lower. The single exception is the European Female group, which is the only one that has a positive mean delta ($M = +0.039$, $t = +3.41$, $p < 0.001$). On the opposite, European Male profiles are the only other group for which the effect is statistically non-significant ($t = -0.94$, $p = 0.349$), suggesting that their identity presents no reliably directional influence on scores in either direction. At the opposite extreme, Unknown Male and Unknown Female profiles suffer the greatest suppression, followed by males from Australia/Oceania and Africa, meaning they are highly penalized by the AI.

Table 10. Mean score delta by region and gender identity groups

Region	Gender	Name removal		Full anonymisation		Bias rate (any)	t	p
		M (SD)	Bias %	M (SD)	Bias %			
Unknown	Male	+0.001 (0.408)	7.4%	-0.190 (0.901)	15.7%	19.2%	-7.33	< 0.001
Unknown	Female	+0.048 (0.464)	8.0%	-0.175 (0.909)	16.6%	20.1%	-6.37	< 0.001
Australia/Oceania	Male	+0.001 (0.335)	6.2%	-0.153 (0.769)	11.5%	14.6%	-7.60	< 0.001
Africa	Male	+0.012 (0.471)	7.6%	-0.131 (0.741)	10.9%	14.9%	-9.79	< 0.001
Australia/Oceania	Female	+0.045 (0.471)	8.4%	-0.126 (0.798)	12.7%	16.9%	-5.89	< 0.001
North America	Male	+0.034 (0.462)	7.4%	-0.108 (0.757)	12.3%	15.6%	-6.69	< 0.001
Asia	Male	+0.008 (0.467)	6.8%	-0.079 (0.800)	11.5%	14.9%	-5.33	< 0.001
Africa	Female	+0.059 (0.491)	8.7%	-0.060 (0.708)	11.9%	16.2%	-4.70	< 0.001
South America	Female	+0.070 (0.525)	9.2%	-0.057 (0.754)	12.5%	16.9%	-2.31	0.021
South America	Male	+0.017 (0.525)	7.7%	-0.057 (0.722)	11.8%	15.5%	-2.31	0.021
North America	Female	+0.097 (0.541)	8.7%	-0.036 (0.679)	11.1%	15.6%	-2.45	0.014
Asia	Female	+0.067 (0.536)	7.8%	-0.029 (0.665)	10.6%	14.3%	-2.38	0.017
Europe	Male	+0.015 (0.456)	6.8%	-0.012 (0.701)	10.8%	13.7%	-0.94	0.349
Europe	Female	+0.067 (0.535)	7.6%	+0.039 (0.605)	10.3%	13.1%	+3.41	< 0.001

We provide the DAG diagram for inferred causal dependencies of bias manifestation, in Figure 9. The strongest upstream determinants of bias are employment status and model architecture, both of which exhibit Cramér’s V values exceed those of all demographic variables. Performance rating and geographic region both show statistically significant associations with presence of bias, confirming their roles as active structural contributors to its formation process. Gender, by contrast, does not demonstrate a significant direct association with bias incidence, indicating that its influence on scoring distortion operates exclusively through indirect pathways, specifically through its association with regional distribution, rather than as a direct determinant.

Figure 9. DAG for inferred causal dependencies

The cells from the pairwise Cramér’s V matrix presented in Figure 10 confirm that model architecture and employment status are the variables most strongly associated with the bias outcome, with all other variables demonstrating weaker but non-trivial associations. The almost zero values for Gender–Bias and Gender–Model confirm that gender does not co-vary with model assignment (as expected by experimental design) and does not independently drive bias activation. The Region–Department association ($V = 0.025$) reflects a realistic structural dependency in the underlying employee data, as different geographic regions influence modestly different departmental distributions, which is incorporated into the DAG as a background edge between professional-tier nodes.

In Figure 11, we present the conditional bias probabilities as a function of employment status and performance rating. Employment status is the strongest professional-tier predictor ($V=0.140$), with *Terminated* and *Resigned* profiles attracting higher bias rates than *Active* profiles across all three models. This pattern is consistent with the hypothesis that status signals interact with identity cues to amplify evaluative distortion. Profiles already marked as having left the organisation carry stronger implicit associations that interact with demographic identifiers in the models’ scoring. Performance rating shows a significant relationship with bias incidence, because employees rated either very low or very high, are more likely to have their scores changed when demographic information is present, compared to employees with mid-range ratings. It suggests that when an LLM is already leaning toward a very strong or very weak evaluation, knowing the employee’s identity may push that judgment even further in the same direction.

Figure 10. Cramér's V pairwise association matrix

Figure 11. Conditional probability of bias P(Bias | Region) by LLM architecture

The DAG and associated conditional probability analyses generate three principal causal inferences. First, model architecture and employment status are the dominant structural determinants of bias probability, both exhibiting Cramér's V values of approximately 0.13–0.14. This finding indicates that the most powerful predictors of whether an LLM evaluation will be affected by identity are architectural choices made during model development and the employment background encoded in the profile, not the raw demographic attributes of gender or region.

Second, demographic variables operate as upstream exogenous nodes in the causal graph but with structurally differentiated pathways: region shows a direct, statistically significant influence on bias incidence and score delta magnitude, whereas gender operates exclusively through indirect pathways (via

regional distribution), exhibiting no significant direct effect. This distinction is important because it implies that regional identity signals, not gender signals, are the active demographic drivers of LLM scoring distortion in this dataset.

Third, the conditional probability distributions confirm that the DAG's structural relationships are not purely statistical abstractions. They manifest significant differences in bias exposure found at each group's level. Profiles from geographically ambiguous backgrounds, with non-active employment status and evaluated by higher-bias-rate architectures face elevated probabilities of receiving a score affected mistakenly by its identity. These findings establish a coherent causal account of LLM bias formation in which architectural and contextual factors amplify the evaluative distortions introduced by identity signals, with implications for employee's privacy.

5. Conclusions

The results of this study offer empirical justification for the data minimization practices mandated by the GDPR, specifically Article 5(1)(c), which requires personal data to be limited to what is strictly necessary for processing purposes. Our analysis demonstrates that for the purpose of predictive analytics in human resources, personal identifiers are demonstrably unnecessary. Their removal preserves algorithmic performance while mitigating demographic bias. The predictive modeling phase confirmed that ML algorithms can accurately forecast AI-generated bias triggers (achieving 92.1% accuracy and 0.943 ROC-AUC with a Random Forest classifier), proving that discriminatory outcomes in LLMs are systemic structural flaws rather than stochastic hallucinations. Moreover, the Bayesian Causality shows that European Female profiles are the only identity group to receive a net score benefit from identity disclosure, making them a clear privileged reference position. Also, the worst-performing groups (Unknown, Australia/Oceania, Africa) are penalised not because of their gender coding but because of their regional association.

The comparative evaluation of Llama3.2, Mistral-Nemo and Gemma3 reveals that, although all three LLMs are capable of performing tasks from the HR sector under an architecture that preserves privacy, they generate discernible differences in behavioral stability and sensitivity to personal identifiers. Importantly, these differences emerge despite the use of identical datasets, prompts and inference parameters.

Consequently, it is important to emphasize that no single model can be considered inherently *compliant* or *safe* in isolation. Instead, the results reinforce the necessity of embedding LLMs within a broader architecture focused on privacy that includes robust anonymization, access control mechanisms and continuous bias monitoring. From a regulatory standpoint, this cross-model comparison provides quantitative support for the EU AI Act's emphasis on suitability testing, risk assessment and ongoing evaluation of high-risk AI systems used in employment. The observed variations demonstrate that benchmarking is not a purely technical optimization exercise, but a necessary governance practice enabling organizations to substantiate due diligence, accountability and proportionality.

The methodology presented in this study provides a replicable, empirically validated framework for demonstrating that privacy-preserving data transformations successfully dismantle the causal pathways of discrimination, protecting candidate equity without degrading analytical utility. Further, navigating the intersection of AI innovation and HR ethics requires recognizing that responsible AI deployment is not merely a function of selecting the right model, but of engineering the precise socio-technical safeguards required to govern it.

Also, Recital 26 of the GDPR clarifies that the principles of data protection do not apply to anonymous information, defined as "*information which does not relate to an identified or identifiable natural person*". By removing direct identifiers and demonstrating that the resulting dataset supports equivalent analytical functionality, organizations may argue that the processed data falls outside the scope of GDPR regulation, thereby reducing compliance burden while maintaining analytical utility, emphasizing the importance of human oversight and accountability in AI system deployment.

The methodology presented in our study provides a replicable framework for validating that privacy-preserving data transformations do not inadvertently degrade model performance, thereby supporting the documentation and auditability requirements of the regulatory framework. Beyond regulatory compliance,

this research also addresses concerns about AI bias and discrimination. When ML models are trained on data containing personal identifiers, there exists a risk, however small, that models may learn spurious correlations between identifiers and outcomes that encode historical biases. By training models exclusively on anonymized data, we may eliminate this risk, contributing to the development of AI systems that are both effective and equitable. This aligns with the *ethics by design principle*, ensuring that AI judgment remains anchored in professional merit rather than social descriptors.

Our findings carry significant implications for organizations seeking to balance analytical objectives with privacy obligations. The demonstrated equivalence of model performance on original and anonymized datasets provides empirical justification for data minimization practices, supports compliance with GDPR and EU AI Act requirements and contributes to the broader project of developing AI systems that are both effective and ethically sound. Future research may extend this analysis to additional prediction tasks, alternative anonymization techniques and diverse organizational contexts, further strengthening the evidence base for privacy-preserving ML practices.

Declarations

Funding-This work was supported by a grant of the Ministry of Research, Innovation and Digitization, CNCS/CCCDI-UEFISCDI, project number COFUND-CETP-SMART-LEM-1, within PNCDI IV. This paper was co-financed by The Bucharest University of Economic Studies during the PhD Program.

Acknowledgement-This work was supported by a grant of the Ministry of Research, Innovation and Digitization, CNCS/CCCDI-UEFISCDI, project number COFUND-CETP-SMART-LEM-1, within PNCDI IV. This paper was co-financed by The Bucharest University of Economic Studies during the PhD Program.

Conflicts of interest/Competing interests-The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

Ethics approval-Not applicable

Consent to participate-Not applicable

Consent for publication-Not applicable

Availability of data and material-Data will be available on request.

Authors' contributions-C.I, S.V.O: Conceptualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing–Original Draft, Writing–Review and Editing, Visualization, Project administration. C.I, A.B, D.M.I: Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Resources, Data Curation, Writing–Original Draft, Writing–Review and Editing, Visualization, Supervision.

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